

Quality and transparency in the Swiss hospital services after the introduction of a DRG-based reimbursement system

Christoph Napierala* Stefan Boes†

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Abstract

Among other factors the Swiss healthcare policy change in 2012 introduced a diagnosis-related groups (DRG) inpatient payment system a change from prior reimbursement models, mainly daily fees, systems. This crucial step created significant momentum allowing the increase of transparency and efficiency in the delivery of acute inpatient services. But little is known about its effects on quality and transparency within health care system.

We use administrative data of inpatient stays of Swiss university hospitals, and qualitative indicators like case mortality as well as transparency measures e.g. number of diagnostic codes per case, and coded and real emergencies to demonstrate the impacts it had comparing the the various retrospective reimbursement systems with the new prospective DRG system. We provide indicative evidence that short-term quality has not suffered from the system change while in the meantime transparency has increased. Lacking further evidence, we can derive that the system change has brought along an improved documentation effort which implicitly support the strive for quality improvements along the patient journey.

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*Corresponding author. University of Lucerne, Center for Health, Policy and Economics, Frohburgstrasse 3, CH-6002 Lucerne, Switzerland, email: napierala@gmx.net.

†University of Lucerne, Department of Health Sciences and Health Policy and Center for Health, Policy and Economics, Frohburgstrasse 3, PO Box 4466, CH-6002 Lucerne, Switzerland, phone: +41 41 229 5949, fax: +41 41 229 5685, email: stefan.boes@unilu.ch.

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1 Introduction

In 2012, the Swiss diagnosis-related groups (DRG) implementation changed the inpatient finance system from a nationwide mix of reimbursement systems (with both retrospective and prospective payment systems) to a harmonized model for all approximately 300 hospitals. At the end of 2011, about four main systems could be distinguished. One where the hospital received a global amount for a service area, where the insurer and the canton (i.e., administrative region) disbursed a fixed amount per case. Another represented a relatively strict APDRG regime used from both financing parties (which we use as a classifier for our referral group). The third applied per diems from the payors side and a global budget covering the cantonal share. The last model represents a mixture of process-oriented payments with a global budget based on APDRG. The complexity of the system was then enhanced by differing reimbursement shares by insurers and cantons. These manifold systems led to issues in controlling policy developments, a lack of cost transparency, and difficulty comparing quality and hospital services; all of which made a change unavoidable.

In the new system, all inpatient stays that are financed through the common social insurance system are reimbursed by health insurers with a share of 45% and by cantons with a maximum of 55% contrary to the not harmonized cantonal shares before.

The APDRG system has been present in most Western Swiss cantons, but not all hospitals have applied it in their reimbursement schemes (e.g., the Canton of Bern, where the university hospital applied APDRG and smaller hospitals did not; and the Canton of Zurich, where the APDRG system was only used for benchmark reasons but with no further effect on reimbursement). Another important difference is that before the reform costs, only patients resident in that canton and being treated in a general ward were covered through the mandatory health insurance, whereas patients can now attend any ward¹. Furthermore, the disbursement of infrastructure subsidies should be restricted only to services where, for example, regional health service needs to be upheld. In general terms, the object-oriented financing was abandoned for the benefit of a more subject (or case-oriented) financing system²

With this change, the policymakers targeted several dimensions. The main aim of such a performance-oriented system is to control cost development, increase efficiency, improve healthcare quality provision, and increase transparency within the system (Braun, Rau and Tuschen, 2007). One of the main policy aims was to increase transparency and data quality to base future policy decisions on more robust baselines.

At this stage, there are only a few indications about the effects of this implementation for Switzerland. Neither the feared increase of cases in certain hospital types (BAG; Pellegrini and Roth; P. Widmer, P. Hochuli, et al.(2015; 2016; 2017)) nor a shift from inpatient to the outpatient sector (Felder et al., 2014) could be demonstrated. Nor is there conclusive information

¹There apply few administrative hurdles but we argue from a principle point of view.

²Further detail about the Swiss healthcare system can be obtained in (Camenzind, 2013) and (De Pietro et al., 2015)

available on quality, despite the measures proposed by Frick, Krischker and G.(2013). The subsequent reports (D. Kohler, M. Widmer and Weaver, 2015; Hedinger, Tuch and M. Widmer, 2017) mainly highlight the development of acute stays and the switch to specialized treatment institutions, without inferring quality indicators based on the policy change.

Other factors also influence efforts to achieve the policy goals (e.g., transparency on up-coding or right-coding) but have been, so far, very little investigated in the Swiss context. The same holds true for other proxies reflected in the literature, such as poor hospital performance on weekends or mortality comparisons. What is still missing is robust evidence on the development potential, where pitfalls in the valuation of such systems can be controversial, for example, comparing mortality rates in hospitals and using them for pay-per-performance models ((Mackenzie et al., 2016)). The challenge is to establish a link between transparency and, for example, reasons for adapted coding practice, which represent a quality driver, at least indirectly. We deem the discussion relevant as major reproaches against the DRG system persist and have for example been raised very early by (e.g. Kahn et al., 1990; Rogers et al., 1990) how focus mainly on increased numbers of early dismissals and their relation to the quality of healthcare. But there is also the strain in literature who look into up-coding (Steinbusch et al., 2007; Schönfelder, Balázs and Klewer, 2009, we use German references as their system is best comparable to the Swiss one) or other elements manipulating the "DRG creep" (Pongpirul and Robinson, 2017, talk of '3C': corporate, clinical, and coding practices). Both investigation lines could hint at a relation to the usage of higher numbers of diagnostic codes in order to sustain their respective claims. These moral hazard issues have been discussed in the literature but mostly remain unresolved.

Those arguments lead to the target of our investigation in the next section.

2 Objective

Taking the issues raised in our introductory section into consideration we propose a comprehensive approach tackling several of the above subjects.

We propose an alternative approach bringing together evaluation criteria within the present policy setup to bridge the gap between current findings and supplement evidence. The aim is to identify correlating factors to policy change where we will show the influence on quality of care through amendments to the transparency of the overall system.

At first we will assemble indicators that will support our analysis. To this mean we will employ several dimensions of quality from a more clinical point of view by using the development of mortality as outcome proxy. From a more structural and process aspect enhancing the transparency argument are the number of diagnostic codes per case on average and the assessment of admission status like emergency and weekdays. Furthermore, the analysis will provide evidence on the changing behavior between two types of hospital classes and not to the raw policy effect.

We will shed light on these under-researched items. We will mainly focus on policy implementation effects on hospital mortality and evaluate this considering various confounding factors, such as weekend and emergency admission. Despite the approach being criticized (Lilford and Pronovost, 2010), we use mortality rates to test the policy effect. Because we are not focusing on comparison or ranking of the hospitals but rather on the policy effect itself, we deem this a valid approach. Additionally, we will focus on the transparency target with respect to quality and will be able to show how the policy influenced the increase in documentation, which is a proxy for improved quality in healthcare (or at least may lead to improved quality).

Our main investigation aims at validating whether the quality of service provision has been affected by the implementation of Swiss DRG in the two types of University hospitals investigated. We also focus on potential bias elements, such as the day of admission (weekend and weekdays) and the type of admission (using emergency admissions as confounding elements). Furthermore, our approach will detect effects on the number of diagnostic codes per case as a proxy for the policy change's transparency aim. As such, we offer a panoply of analysis items that will provide evidence on policy implementation effects on both quality and transparency.

One of the main limitations we find in this context is that we do not dispose of readily available data that would allow looking beyond the crude inpatient mortality rates [e.g., 30 days mortality, which is not available in Switzerland (noted for example also in Taylor, 2013)]. Nevertheless, because we do not compare the hospitals themselves – rather the policy impact – it will be sufficient to focus on the hospital mortality rates. We also lack more detailed data on cost and personnel, that would allow us for more detailed findings in resource use and how this could correlate with rates. We will also look at a disease-driven dimension, where we use episodes of care (EoC) to detect differences in the respective behavior after the policy change on weighted mortality and the other transparency measures.

Secondly, we will use the emergency admission categories to discover changes that have been triggered by the new policy, as well as how the use of diagnostic codes has been triggered by the policy change.

Lastly, we test whether the care quality on weekends has been altered by the implementation of DRG into the Swiss healthcare system, but independently of the policy change.

We will proceed with our discussion by introducing our data source and issues, followed by the method part. Then, the analysis of results is presented, and we conclude with a discussion of findings.

3 Data Handling and Enrichment

The data used for this study was gathered from the Swiss Federal Office of Statistics and represents the medicals statistic's hospital data from 2011 to 2013 and contains a total of 4,091,632 data entries. Hospitals can only be identified through their type and number of cases; due to confidentiality issues, the regional attribution is not contained. We classified APDRG

and non-APDRG university hospitals containing 640,221 observations by aligning them to the respective corporate reports and excluded the remaining hospitals from our analysis because those providers cannot be attributed to either the counterfactual or treatment group.

Based on Table 6, we can, for instance, see that the yearly pooled inpatient mortality rates are very similar in all hospital types. Other covariates are graphically represented in Figure 9, and despite the differences in levels, we can show parallel pre-trends in both analyzed hospital groups looking at the quarterly data. Also, some factors, such as the differences in the number of treatment or the number of diagnostic codes per case, could hint at differences in the patient pathways. Those elements will be shown in our later analysis. In general, we can, however, say that our treatment and control grouped hospitals can be compared without further stratification or matching needs at this stage.

We have re-grouped all the data to the 2012 reference DRG catalog. This allows us to compare all DRG cases through time and with the same base, and to potentially compare pathways Schreyögg et al.(2014), which in our case is less important. However, this disregards adaptations in coding treatment and diagnostic data, which can depend on the yearly amendments and for which we cannot correct. Nevertheless, harmonizing all our available yearly data eliminates other noise, such as the yearly change in the attribution of, for example, diagnostic codes to a specific DRG code.

Among the source data, 511,831 cases were attributed to psychiatric (M500), geriatric (M900) or physical medicine or rehabilitation (M950) wards³ and were discarded from our analysis. We eliminate 34,484 data entries with clinically untypical information⁴ and limit our data to University hospitals due to identification matters. Furthermore, we will refrain from using the non-university institutions as an artificial comparison as we deem them to be biased in both the regional and group attribution, and would thus add noisy information to our discussion, thus excluding a further 2,853,961 cases from our set, resulting in a total of 558,019 analyzed entries.

For analysis matters, we proceeded to an aggregation of data using the hospital type, year and quarter, weekend, DRG, patient class, and EoC. Our main outcome variables expressed in rates are mortality, emergency, real emergency rate⁵, and number of diagnostic codes per case. The accumulated cases are respectively put in relation to the grouped total number of cases⁶.

4 Method

We take advantage of the specific changes in the healthcare financing system in Switzerland described in the above introduction in Chapter 1. More specifically there were areas with hospitals having an APDRG (All Patient DRG) reimbursement system in place for several

³This procedure corresponds to the one chosen in M. Widmer and Weaver(2011).

⁴i.e., all DRG codes starting with 9

⁵We classify real emergencies as patients that are admitted "horizontally" to the hospital being an emergency

⁶applying the general formula $n_{\text{Deceased}_{\text{DRG}_i}} / n_{\Sigma \text{ cases}_{\text{DRG}_i}}$

years, and others that had no such system. This allows for an identification strategy, which is required within an experiment. These early-adopting hospitals will represent the control group to the treatment group hospitals, where DRG will have been freshly implemented. Due to data protection and consequent identification issues, we must restrict the data to University hospitals. As these are evenly distributed through Switzerland, we can assume that they do represent a valid sample with regards to both regional and other time-varying effects. Thus, we apply a similar identification strategy to the one chosen by Felder et al.(2014) but with a more careful focus on university hospitals to avoid potential endogeneity or bias through wrong attribution of institutions that cannot be controlled for. The danger of attributing other hospital types wrongly would distort results at the cost of losing observations (compared to Chapter 2).

Using such a (DiD) in the Swiss context is not new(Felder et al., 2014; Papanicolas and McGuire, 2015) nor is the identification strategy (Boes and Gerfin, 2013). Our approach will permit insights into the functioning of the policy on very little researched dimensions, especially with a rather short-term focus.

As time fixed effect (FE), we will employ the period (i.e., the first year will be 2012, after the policy implementation). The treatment fixed effect we are controlling for is the hospitals that have not previously had (APDRG), versus those having had the (DRG) precursor⁷:

$$\text{Mortality}_{st} = \lambda + \lambda_1 \text{APDRG}_s + \lambda_2 \text{Year}_t + \tau \text{APDRG}_s * \text{Year}_t + X'_{st} + \epsilon_{st} \quad (1)$$

The outcome variable is the average mortality rate per pooled element i . Where we are required by the analysis to substitute the outcome accordingly (e.g., with the number of diagnosis codes), keeping the right side of the equation stable. APDRG_1 indicates our treatment variable per case i.e., here per aggregated element (denoted by the subscript s), and APDRG_0 indicates non-treatment or in general terms the control group effect. In order to show the policy effects, we use years as our time FE. Year_t denotes the year time period. 2011 will stand for the pre-treatment year and 2012 denotes the year of the implementation. Our DiD effect is defined by the interaction term $\text{APDRG}_s * \text{Year}$ or average treatment effect of the treated ($\text{ATET} = \tau$,) measuring short term impact of the introduction of SwissDRG on the respective outcome variable. ϵ_{st} represents unobserved characteristics independent of APDRG_s and Year_t . Significance levels were set at the 5% level using the student t-test (where not otherwise stated). Statistical analysis was performed using R software versions and the libraries used are listed in the appendix of Chapter 9.

The DiD model's two main assumptions avoiding bias are that the dependent variable would have developed in the same way for both types of hospitals would the policy change not have occurred, and, there are not other parallel influences (e.g. other policies or different technological levels). The first assumption is impossible to test directly but for example figure 8 allows us to distinguish between the parallel trend before the implementation, where the number of cases

⁷Compare (Imbens and Wooldridge, 2007, p. 2) which have used a similar model to 1

per hospital has shifted with little differential before the policy change for the five university hospitals. This is also the case for further indicators. We can, therefore, exclude a violation of this crucial assumption (see Figure 9). Different trends before the implementation would imply that the average change in outcome variable for the DRG group in the absence of the Swiss DRG implementation was equal to the one in the APDRG group. For example, we can observe a general trend of LOS reduction all through Switzerland, documented for example in Busato and von Below(2010) and OECD(2018), not only due to the DRG system but already prevalent before its inception. Also, the development of case numbers in our sample shows a similar behavior all through our observation periods (refer to Figure 1 and 8). This allows the conclusion that our sample behaved similarly before, and we can exclude unobserved variable influence. Secondly, and, despite the fact that the APDRG system was mainly used in the Western Swiss region, we can assume that a potential endogeneity is well captured because one of the counterfactual hospitals is based in the same region type (language and culture) as the treatment group hospitals, and thus makes the distribution within the single variables comparable (see Table 6). Another critical point is whether one can compare the two systems overall despite their slightly different setups? According to **brugger'impact'2010(brugger'impact'2010)**, their built is comparable, and thus we assume that this allows our model's key assumption to uphold.

We have adapted the model by Imbens and Wooldridge(2007) to account for the potential heteroscedasticity by applying a weighted least square (WLS) model using the number of cases per aggregated group. The latter is also necessary for a meaningful interpretation of the model's size effects due to the aggregated data.

In our discussion, and, in general one of the most critical questions (Angrist and J. Pischke, 2009) is the selection of the treatment and control group. Which we solved by diligently identifying the hospitals manually and grouping them as such. As mentioned above, we can most probably rule out regional fixed effects as one of our hospitals in the control group is part of the treatment group's region but has applied APDRG before the overall Swiss implementation. Furthermore, our groups remain stable over time. We also apply placebo periods to validate the result's robustness (e.g., model 4 in Table 3). However, one of the largest drawbacks of our study is the weak data basis before the implementation. This can only hardly be remedied and has been investigated in another discussion(P. Widmer, Trottmann, et al., 2017) where data series have been proved to be unstable before 2011 and hardly comparable with the later years.

Potential other breaches in the assumptions with regard to contrasts in the specific regions of the respective hospitals can be excluded. This despite the overall differences in the rate levels persisting after the DRG implementation. This shows the regional variation in medical (Camenzind, 2012) or technological practice in the main regions as well as for examples switches in health care provision from inpatient to outpatient structures (Felder et al., 2014) due to the policy change.

In order to control for further endogeneity we add a minimal vector (X') of covariates additionally

Figure 1: Quarterly Development of Number of Cases in University Hospitals

Note:

The figure displays the summarized and neutralized five Swiss university hospitals quarterly cases' number development split in APDRG and non-APDRG.

The figure depicts the relatively stable case development in Switzerland through time on a quarterly basis.

to a FE model implicitly avoiding omitted time-invariant characteristics (U. Kohler and Kreuter, 2005) using DRG.

Three subsets of covariates are being employed in our model. At first we add demographic patient elements like gender and age. Then we add patient's administrative detail like insurance class, what type of emergency admission, the patient clinical complexity level (PCCL), and we added the classification of the outlying type a patient was i.e. whether he was classified as an inlier or outlier case. In order to distinguish patient case types beyond the DRG coding we added (EoC). On the diagnosis side by mapping of ICD codes to comorbidities (congestive heart failure, cholecystectomy, hernia, pulmonary and stroke cases) using the papers by Quan et al.(2005) an extension of Deyo, Cherkin and Ciol(1992) and applying a fitting R package Wasey(2017) which provides us with the largest patient groups. For treatments we identified the CHOP codes(Swiss surgery codes) for knee and hip surgery and derived the EoC. All non-attributable and remaining cases have been attributed to an EoC class "Other" which itself serves as a reference group. We are intentionally including EoC that have low mortality rates (i.e. hip and knee interventions) in order to control for potential endogeneity. The last block represent clinically and patient pathway relevant indicators like weighted number of diagnosis (squared), treatments(squared), artificial respiration hours(squared), hours of intensive care unit stay(squared), and length of stay (LOS). Additional factors are the Charlson Comorbidity Group Index (CCI) ⁸(Charlson et al., 1987), intensive care unit(ICU) hours, and the number of artificial respiration hours provided to the case. These factors allow an improved assessment of severity of the single case. However after having tested these covariates we conclude that only a minimum will add sensitivity to our estimates avoiding implicit co-linearity and not reducing

⁸Comorbidity is an independent, additional condition adding to the primary diagnosis and is calculated in an algorithm we use ICD10 Sundararajan et al.(2004) applying the R package by Wasey(2017)

bias. This consequence has also been described in literature (e.g. Xie et al., 2016; Laursen et al., 2016; Piscator et al., 2016) concluding that most of our available factors are associated with longer LOS and higher inpatient mortality rates. Although relevant for controlling they potentially only add noise to the analysis (e.g. PCCL⁹) we will limit the model to CCI.

The cross-section sample satisfies the DiD data requirements through time. At this stage we can avoid issues with this by implicitly applying a FE model i.e. to avoid effects linked to implicit characteristics of the case groups in Table 8, which uses mortality rates as outcome variable and using quarterly terms showing the non-existing prior parallel trend and the development of the policy effect after implementation. Equation 2 applies the model used in Autor(2003) and allow for a robustness check of the DiD identification. The results presented in Table 8 show that for model (1) the RMSE is in a range which appears to be reasonable. For the other two outcomes in model (3) and (4) we obtain much higher indicators hinting at un-captured bias. To show the crude effects, we maintain the parsimonious model for all.

We will use minimal sensitivity analysis, applying placebo periods (compare model (3) in Table 8 to validate the assumptions made in Angrist and J. Pischke(2009). The descriptive analysis (5.1 below) does not hint at any nonparallel behaviors in the groups. Briefly, we will check whether the effect on mortality or our other quality proxies is solely observable in the period of implementation, thus avoiding bias in our DiD analysis. The main objective of using this methodological approach is to show that the policy changes had an impact on outcome rates, despite the short overall observation period.

Below we report the results of our assessment and effect sizes.

5 Analysis and Results

In general, we expect that the hospitals not having had a DRG system in place before the policy change would not show any significant change in the outcome (e.g., inpatient mortality rates due to the change in the financing system of Switzerland). However, we expect a distinctive improvement in documentation quality and through this an increased quality within the inpatient healthcare system. Below we infer consequences on quality of healthcare provision, validating our expectancies.

5.1 Descriptive Findings

5.1.1 Findings on mortality rates

As seen in Table 6, the mean of weighted inpatient mortality appears to be similar for both the treatment and control group. But there also seems to be an adaptation process happening in both groups, probably having been set off by the policy change, where differences either

⁹Complexity level a patient's DRG case from 0 to 4.

partly converge or not, where we assume these being effects stemming from different treatment regimes described and referenced above.

Looking at the quarterly evolution of the weighted mortality in Figure 2 , we see that the change at the moment of the system implementation was moderate. We consider the spikes in both groups in quarters one in 2012 and four in 2014 to be random effects, which account for the sensitivity of the rates due to the low overall numbers of deceased patients (i.e., a small increase in the numerator or a reduction in the number of cases can alter the rate substantially). With the current data at hand, however, we cannot deduct the reasons for such developments nor can we derive other shifts or shocks in the healthcare provision, as we would require complete mortality data for all institutions. In general, we can observe stable inpatient mortality rates and alignment of all hospitals towards the end of our observation period. These results are sound from an intuitive point-of-view, as the more difficult cases are referred to university hospitals and these cases can be compared indifferently to the system they are in. However, for all hospital types, the closeness to other institutions, such as elderly homes, can be decisive for the hospital mortality rates, but we lack the respective data to allow measuring such factors. Comparing our data with international sources (e.g. Hall, MJ, Levant, S and DeFrances, CJ, 2013; Hines et al., 2015), the Swiss rates per EoC (compare Figure 3 show similar numbers. However, individual country characteristics in structures of healthcare provision impede a straightforward comparison.

We also suspect a learning effect, both for coding and for organizing a transfer to other institutions for the respective patients (i.e., to reduce the cost burden and high outlier cases); this was previously proposed by Napierala and Boes(2017). Furthermore, we can also assume a lower boundary of inpatient death rates, which cannot go below a certain threshold. The last periods in our chart appear to provide such a number, acknowledging the lacking evidence for its size.

With the limited number of periods in our analysis, especially the pre-treatment periods, these trends have to be cautiously pondered, but one can still assume their robustness as similar movements can be observed at least for the comparison group and the treatment group (i.e., non-APDRG hospitals). At this moment we do not know of any other effect other than a time trend affecting a specific healthcare region where the sample hospitals are situated. In the same period, we can observe a reduction of use of treatment places for elderly people (> 80 -years-old) but with no obvious regional difference. (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2015)

Analyzing hospitals further in Table 6, the behaviors of the chosen covariates show no relevant differentials. Thus, our analysis will not require a matching strategy only having a marginal effect on ruling-out potential endogeneity.

Nevertheless, breaking the clinical cases to the more suitable brackets of Episodes of Care (EoC) allow us to deepen the analysis and underpins our findings (compare Figure 3 and Table 7), especially in the "Other" category, where the unclassified cases do not show any apparent inferred policy effect.

Figure 2: Mortality rates in APDRG and non-APDRG hospitals by quarter

Note:

The figure displays the aggregated quarterly relative hospital mortality split into APDRG and non-APDRG groups.

Figure 3: Selected EoC depicting the policy effect on mortality by year

Note:

The figure displays the aggregated quarterly relative hospital mortality split into APDRG and non-APDRG groups.

The EoC chosen represents the most prevalent diagnostics from an interventional and internal perspective

It is worth noting that the differences in mortality levels within our comparison groups appear to be at random and very similar to other countries' university hospitals. Generally, other hospital categories have lower mortality rates, except for the more straightforward interventions like hip, hernia or cholecystectomies, which are dealt with in the more general hospitals and thus would also have higher mortality. This is due to other case profiles and treatment regimes, as well as the fact that universities are in charge of cases that cannot be dealt with in general hospitals. This also represents the main criticism of the current Swiss DRG setup (H. Hochuli P.,

P. Widmer and Telser, 2017). For our analysis, though it is of relevance that the universities appear to align their mortality rates in all areas over time, which shows that the system change induces a change in the treatment regime and thus implicitly a more congruent treatment (i.e., service quality within similar structures and providers).

5.1.2 The influence of the day of the week and emergency admissions

We also suspect that weekdays influence the policy effect, as described in Napierala and Boes(2017). Also hinting at differentiated risk patterns on weekends that could improve quality of services if diligently dealt with (such as described in Concha et al., 2014, who propose identification for different risk patterns improving quality).

In fact, looking at the Figure 4, higher mortality on weekends is prevalent in all cases, but differences in panel (1) and (2) appear to be rather small and develop in quasi-synchronicity. This is despite the second being an emergency and generally understood as cases 'at risk' of dying. The only difference appears in panel (3) for weekdays, where the non-APDRG hospitals display an increase in mortality rate, which is maintained. This does hint at changed patient processes compared to the control group. Despite the small difference, this will prove to be significant, as we will see later. Contrary to the case study's results on efficiency cited above, overall mortality appears to remain stable in all admission status. Pursuing the analysis of confounding factors into weekends (Concha et al., 2014) combined with emergency treatments, which would be suspected to increase inpatient mortality (Figure 4). It seems that all hospitals types tend to align their mortality through time, or at least differences appear to be insignificant, also contrary to their coding practice. These findings indicate that, for patients a more dedicated treatment path, provided by an improved and transparent coding practice, pays-off in the long run. Seeing these small and overall insignificant consequences, it could also be a sign that the policy did not have a negative impact on putting the patient at risk.

This effect has so far not been described in the literature and would correspond to intuition as the coded entries should not largely differ by type of weekday. This argument is further underpinned by the graph 5, which shows the rates per coded groups. Seemingly with no policy change influencing the real emergency rates (right panel of Figure 5) but with a slight difference in behavior in the coded cases (left panel). Here it seems that different documentation patterns induced this change, as we see a rather stable behavior for the "real" emergencies¹⁰, where the differences in level are maintained, but the reduction pattern is in both comparable. Stipulating parallel effects by the policy but different patient pathways, mortality rates and the number of emergency type admissions in Figure 5 display a differentiated behavior within the hospital system where the two university groups behave differently. The first difference is the larger drop in the APDRG group of coded emergency rates, whereas, in the treatment group, the rates appear to be rather stable but at a far lower level. All this is an indication of the above-mentioned differences in treatment patterns throughout Switzerland, but foremost it

¹⁰Cases that were classified as emergency cases and admitted "horizontally"

Figure 4: Yearly mortality rates compared to cases' emergency and weekday admission status

Note:

The figure displays the aggregated quarterly relative hospital mortality split into APDRG and non-APDRG groups.

The cases have been categorized into elective cases, emergency coded cases, and cases that were emergency coded and entered the hospital horizontally, for which we use the terminology "real emergency".

shows that the policy inflicted changes in coding behavior by aligning coding behavior in both types almost in parallel.

This can potentially lead to two conclusions. First, the policy seems to have had an effect on documenting and decreased the number of cases as emergencies in APDRG hospital compared to non-APDRG hospitals, who continue at the same level of emergency coded cases for weekdays but at lower levels for weekends. If the clinical portfolio has not seen any changes, this would mean that the policy has induced a change. Second, the rate of "real" emergencies decreases for both the counterfactual and treatment groups, in parallel. But the difference between weekends and weekdays is maintained, with the non-APDRG hospitals having higher "real emergency" admissions. The SwissDRG coding guidelines do not show any difference before and after for either the "real" emergency cases nor the coded ones. The handbook even stipulates an effect of emergencies on the respective case group (i.e., DRG code (SwissDRG, 2018)), but there is no change in coding guideline with the implementation, which would entail the impossibility of up-coding through the emergency classification of a case. Thus, we can only assume a change in documentation requirements supporting the case management in hospitals. The parametric analysis described below will further focus on these elements. Coding of emergencies in the administrative process appears to be relevant, as mortality rate behavior between the "real" and "coded" emergencies differs significantly. But it can also be shown through the tendentially surging "real" emergency rates, at least for the non-APDRG group, compared to the coded emergency rates.

Figure 5: Yearly coded and real emergencies rates by hospital group

Note:

The figure displays the aggregated quarterly relative hospital emergency admissions split into APDRG and non-APDRG groups.

The data shows the grouped rate development of emergency type admissions in each hospital type.

The cases have been categorized into elective cases, emergency coded cases, and cases that were emergency coded and entered the hospital horizontally. We only display the non-elective cases as, when talking about the number of entries per type, the counterfactual can be deduced from the emergency coded cases.

We propose three principal reasons for this peculiar behavior of emergencies. First, emergency coded cases will tendentially end-up in higher DRG groups (i.e., result in a higher remuneration and thus reduced in numbers less heavily than the "real" cases). However, it seems that the APDRG group's change stems from a pre-existing diverse coding and treatment regime. Neither the APDRG rule set nor the instruction documents provide an indication why this pronounced reduction occurred. Secondly, with the implementation of the DRG system, transparency targets require from coding practice an increased level of precision, and thus cases might result in a coded emergency without necessarily being a real emergency case or not to be classified any longer, which appears to be the case in the current data set. Hospital staff confirms that diligence in coding largely improved with the new policy. Thirdly, hospitals want to be able to prove that there is a high influx of emergency cases that weight heavily on their general cost profiles. This is to show that the remuneration is to low. Again, we would have expected an increase instead of the overall reduction in both coded and real emergency cases; even though base rates (i.e., the unitary case weight prize) are already higher for large parts of Swiss hospitals offering emergency services. Thus, we conclude that the coding quality has improved due to the policy intervention in the sense that codes are being appropriately used. Furthermore, it is redeeming using both dimension interdependently as they appear to suffer different effects from the policy change and both sustain, from their angle, our hypothesis of improved system quality.

5.1.3 Transparency through altered use of diagnostic codes

The under-investigated transparency target is further enhanced by highlighting how hospitals react to the implicit documentation requirements. Insurance, as well as the cantonal reimbursements, are based on good quality documentation at any time reasons for specific codes have to be compliant. The apparent learning effect was that the cases are getting better documented by indicating the diagnosis codes (i.e., ICD-10) and when treatments are involved the according to CHOP code (Swiss surgical codes). These activities directly link the financial result of a case to a qualitative argument, which is the standardized documentation that prevents an eventual cumbersome information request procedure by the payors.

Transparency appears to be even more distinguishable and of increasing relevance when looking at the continuously rising number of diagnostic codes (compare Figure 6).

Figure 6: Average number of diagnostic codes (yearly) per case

Note:

The figure displays the aggregated yearly average number of coded diagnostic codes per case split into APDRG and non-APDRG groups.

The development in the hospital groups is similar but at different levels. A steady increase can be observed in both hospital types; a sign that the system is adopting itself but independently of the policy. This also means that the cases are being described with more accuracy, and thus also describing the single cases with more detail. Medical justification of case's reimbursement can be tracked without the indirect reference to the single case file. This also allows hospitals to comply with increasing demands for health insurers on documentation requirements. On the other hand, this effort could also hint at up-coding; however, we cannot find evidence for this in our context. Should this be the case, one of the main reproaches against a DRG system would be validated. However, this is again questionable as in all hospital groups a similar increase in the number of diagnostic codes is observable and would, in our opinion, hint at a right-coding tendency and strive for correct clinical documentation, rather than increasing the cases' average reimbursement. However, there appears to be at least a correlated increase in the case weight since the implementation of the new policy (Table 1), at least compared on a yearly average. As it happens in all hospital groups, more or less in parallel, this appears to be a system induced

overall increase through time¹¹.

Table 1: Development of average case weight (weighted) per hospital group

Hospital Group	2011Q1	2011Q2	2011Q3	2011Q4	2012Q1	2012Q2	2012Q3	2012Q4	2013Q1	2013Q2	2013Q3	2013Q4
APDRG	1.32	1.32	1.33	1.33	1.39	1.41	1.38	1.35	1.40	1.37	1.39	1.39
non-APDRG	1.41	1.40	1.44	1.41	1.49	1.48	1.47	1.48	1.48	1.46	1.46	1.48

Note:

The values above represent the weighted 'case weight' development per quarter. All case weights have been re-grouped to the 2012 DRG catalog to make them comparable. Multiplied with the respective base rate, one obtains the reimbursed amount per inpatient case.

If we enhance the analysis by splitting the cases into diagnostic codes and categories represented in the graph 7, we obtain a differentiated view. It is noteworthy that we observe similar reactions to the new policy in both our hospital groups. The weekend mortality rate was greater than the weekday mortality rate. Roughly, mortality is also gradually stable in the 'one diagnosis' code group, which largely corresponds to intuition. Because we assume that the number of diagnosis codes increases, especially in more difficult cases not necessarily leading to death, the system implementation has apparently brought along more accurate requirements for documentation (i.e., compare above discussion on emergency coding). However, the higher groups (> 2) indicate that the policy has produced three effects. On weekdays, there is a convergence of mortality in both groups, whereas on weekends the effects are not as clear, most probably due to the short observation times and higher standard errors. Lastly, the weekend mortality appears to converge (with two exceptions) towards the weekday's level, which in itself would be a positive sign for the system overall. Interestingly, there seems to be a clear tendency for weekend admission cases that the group with a very high number of diagnostic codes reduces mortality rates quite significantly. This is likely because of the swap of the patient from acute- to palliative-oriented healthcare institutions. Generally, mortality is a little higher in university hospitals. Thus, the case profile remains to be structurally different from other hospital types, and shows the differing function (i.e., teaching and training) of university hospitals in healthcare provision. But this overall distinguishable change since the policy inception date is in itself a sign of improved transparency and a strive for more quality in the system overall. However, the persisting differences between the two hospital types cannot be explained with the data at hand.

5.2 Model Results

Our parametric analysis has applied the DiD model 1 described above. The summary results in Table 2 display crude policy effects and general tendencies, including covariates in described in our data section above. We have adapted the OLS method (1) by Imbens and Wooldridge(2007), accounting for potential heterogeneity in effects and size by applying a weighted least square (*WLS*) approach using the number of cases per group. Due to our cautious modeling approach, we implicitly accounted for this effect and obtain only a small effect (comparing standardized

¹¹Such a statement has been made possible as all the cases have been re-grouped to the same DRG reference catalog 2012

Figure 7: Mortality rates by groups of diagnostic codes by APDRG and non-APDRG hospitals

Note:

The figure displays the aggregated quarterly average mortality rates per case split into APDRG and non-APDRG groups.

The graph contains weighted mortality rates per hospital type for diagnostic groups based on the number of codes per case.

We distinguish four groups, with the top group representing more than eleven codes per case, the second grouping cases above six, an in-between group of two or more codes, and the cases with only one code.

residuals) with the additional precaution. We further use cluster-robust estimators¹² to cope with the heteroscedasticity effects prevalent in DiD models and discussed in (Angrist and J. Pischke, 2009, p. 294).

The weak explanatory power of the model, however, has to be noted, despite its non-relevance in the case of the DiD model - as its coefficient basically displays the policy effect. Nevertheless, the very small effects point in the same direction and are small because the overall inpatient hospital mortality rate is very small, thereby proving the relevance of your model.

To account for potentially confounding factors, we have enriched the parsimonious model (1) in Table 2 in the next paragraph with the covariates we suspect to be influencing mortality in models (5) to (7), respectively. The identification strategy is restricted to the variables made available by the data source and does though ascertain maximum reliability.¹³

Model (2) and (3) display the weekday effect described above and only show that mortality appears to be higher on weekends but is slightly corrected by time effects, as shown in our above descriptive graphs. The latter appears to be a general development in the healthcare system and cannot be inferred through the policy change. One could also state that if the quality before the change has been appropriate, the system adaptation has resulted in any overall deterioration and, thus, the quality has remained unaffected. On the contrary, the negative

¹² $\omega_i = \frac{v_i^2}{(1-h_i)^2}$ in MacKinnon and White; Long and Ervin(1985; 2000) for minimizing the weight of influential observations

¹³For the full detail of all categories refer to Table 7

sign in the DiD factors (model (1)) show that the influence on the treatment group has been to reduce the mortality rates, although at a very low and barely perceivable level, if at all.

Adding covariates increases the explanatory power of our basic model but it remains overall rather low. This is also an indication of the data’s enrichment potential.

In Table 7, we add a model variant that uses a placebo period approach, where it is shown that the policy did not have a spurious effect using a year later. Thus, hospital mortality has not deteriorated due to the new legal setting - this being a sign for the stability of healthcare provision. Nevertheless, sustained level differences remain difficult to explain.

Table 2: DiD Models on Effects on Mortality and Covariates

	(1) DiD Model (weighted)	(2) Same (1) only weekend	(3) Same (1) only weekdays	(4) Patient Confounders	(5) Administrative Confounders	(6) Same (5) incl. EOC	(7) Clinical all confounders
Intercept	0.0197 (0.0007)***	0.0409 (0.0030)***	0.0176 (0.0007)***	0.0020 (0.0008)**	-0.0019 (0.0009)*	-0.0015 (0.0008)	-0.0379 (0.0015)***
Basic Model							
2012	0.0023 (0.0011)*	-0.0059 (0.0039)	0.0030 (0.0011)**	0.0023 (0.0009)**	0.0015 (0.0009)	0.0012 (0.0008)	0.0011 (0.0013)
2013	0.0007 (0.0011)	-0.0042 (0.0039)	0.0011 (0.0011)	0.0006 (0.0009)	-0.0003 (0.0009)	-0.0006 (0.0009)	-0.0021 (0.0013)
non-APDRG Hospital	0.0002 (0.0011)	0.0014 (0.0045)	0.0004 (0.0011)	-0.0019 (0.0009)*	-0.0009 (0.0009)	-0.0014 (0.0009)	-0.0046 (0.0014)***
ATET 2012	-0.0006 (0.0016)	0.0062 (0.0061)	-0.0012 (0.0017)	-0.0007 (0.0013)	0.0000 (0.0013)	0.0001 (0.0013)	0.0016 (0.0020)
ATET 2013	0.0011 (0.0016)	0.0019 (0.0061)	0.0010 (0.0017)	0.0006 (0.0013)	0.0013 (0.0013)	0.0013 (0.0013)	0.0045 (0.0019)*
Patient Data				YES	YES	YES	YES
Administrative Data					YES	YES	YES
EoC						YES	YES
Clinical Data							YES
Adj. R ²	0.0000	0.0001	0.0001	0.0196	0.0247	0.0340	0.0538
Num. obs.	189674	26871	162803	189674	189674	189674	101841
RMSE	0.2107	0.2447	0.2043	0.2086	0.2081	0.2071	0.2342

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. indicating significance levels with standard errors

Source:

All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group. Furthermore grouping according to the description in chapter 3 using hospital mortality rates as outcome variable.

Note:

Models use the respective years for comparison i.e. implementation effect 2012 is based on data of 2011 and 2012 omitting 2013. That is why the number of observations differ.

We use the weighting factor of n where n represents the number of cases per aggregated group.

All models use robust s.e. and p-values.

All DiD coefficients are calculated based on the pre-implementation year 2011 compared with the first year after the implementation 2012. Including all covariates described.

Model (1) represents the weighted baseline model comparing 2011 weighted mortality to the first quarter 2012.

(2) shows a model based on weekend data only

Model (3) shows a model based on weekday data only

(4) adds patient specific covariates to the model (1) like gender and age. (5) describes the patients administrative data like insurance status, the referring body, weekend admission, status of the patient’s length of stay status: HO = High Outlier Case (reference Inlier); LO = Low Outlier Case (reference Inlier); Mov. = Binding transfer deduction; NV = Not validated as an Outlier Case

Model (6) adds EoC as we suspect them to influence our results acknowledging the addition auto-collinearity to the model the dummy variable reference are "Other" cases nor in the selected list. (CHF = Congestive heart failure).

Model (7) adds the Charlson Comorbidity index as reference clinical indicator to the model.

All covariates are accumulated figures per group (full detail in Table 7).

ATET denotes an interaction term combined of the year and the treatment group as dummies representing the average treatment effect of the treated.

In the following paragraph, we look into the above-mentioned documentation improvement both through the change of utilization of diagnostic codes (refer to Figure 7) and enhancements in the use of the respective emergency coding.

We have applied the same basic DiD models, changing the outcome to the number of diagnostic codes per case in Table 3, which demonstrates that in the short-term, and with the implementation, there is no significant difference within the hospital types, despite the sustained increase of codes shown in the "ATET 2013", which is even higher than in the "ATET 2012". The non-significant coefficients in models (2) and (3) meet assumptions as they both increase but are not being influenced by the policy. This could still indicate a sustained change in documentation requirements, as well as in behavior at all levels. Furthermore, the effect seems to be robust through time, strong, and work-in-progress as the effect is maintained. It would be

interesting to test whether this effect will fade away over time. Our data do not allow such a long-term observation. Model (4) validates with the placebo periods used that there is no effect either in the longer run.

Table 3: DiD Model Using Number of Diagnostic Codes per Case

	(1) DiD number diagnostic codes	(2) same (1) only weekends	(3) same (1) only weekdays	(4) same (1) only 1 quarter before and after
Intercept	4.4460 (0.0789)***	5.2532 (0.1067)***	4.3670 (0.0843)***	4.2424 (0.1438)***
2012	0.2177 (0.1073)*	0.0383 (0.1668)	0.2321 (0.1147)*	0.4973 (0.2023)*
2013	0.2299 (0.1161)*	0.2613 (0.1423)	0.2242 (0.1241)	
non-APDRG Hospital	0.5165 (0.1280)***	0.8092 (0.1357)***	0.5047 (0.1358)***	0.8106 (0.2621)**
ATET 2012	0.0783 (0.1772)	0.1421 (0.2097)	0.0729 (0.1883)	-0.3880 (0.3586)
ATET 2013	0.1640 (0.1799)	0.1088 (0.1921)	0.1686 (0.1911)	
Adj. R ²	0.0073	0.0109	0.0074	0.0098
Num. obs.	189674	26871	162803	31727
RMSE	6.2894	5.5372	6.3861	6.1887

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. indicating significance levels with standard errors

Source:

All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group.

Note:

Models use number of diagnostic codes(weighted) per case group and use robust s.e. and p-values.

We use the weighting factor of n where n represents the number of cases per aggregated group.

Model (1) using year 2011 and 2012.

Model (2) using all available years which shows the same insignificant negative direction of the effect diluting predictability.

Model (3) using all available years which shows the same insignificant negative direction of the effect diluting predictability.

Model (4) using years 2011 and 2013 portraying an supposed term effect like in a placebo model.

ATET denotes an interaction term combined of the year and the treatment group as dummies representing the average treatment effect of the treated.

We have, to account for the potential bias discussed above, further adopted the models in Table 4 by restricting the data set to coded emergency rates at admission, "real" emergencies¹⁴, and into cases that were admitted on weekends. For weekends (see the model (3)) alone, we see that there is no significant policy effect. But then the sign of the DiD factor turns thus indicating that mortality is increased on weekends for our treatment group which corresponds again to the above descriptive findings in figures 5 and 7. Additionally, we distinguish no policy effect when only looking at the rate of emergency admissions in model (1). Both do have a positive sign, which would indicate a higher rate for the non-APDRG hospitals, leading to a new short-term financing system. For the cases in the model (1), we suspect the increased documentation requirements being the reason because it helps to make the hospital relevant from a system point-of-view indicating the increased need for emergency structures. However, it remains unclear why the "real" rates in model decline for the new system hospitals. The rate difference is small.

We do, however, suspect a registration bias, which should again prove that transparency in the medical records is improved. Also, we suspect that "real" emergency rates should have been reduced, which is factually the case based on model (4). If we add weekends to models (5) and (6), and despite the same direction of the DiD factor, we observe that the difference is amplified for the real emergencies and attenuated for the coded ones. This could again be an indication for reduced service levels in university hospitals on weekends and changes in the referral of emergencies. However, we can only speculate on these matters as we would require a link to individual hospital planning schedules. Which is at this stage not linkable to the data at hand.

¹⁴Our definition of "real" emergencies are the cases admitted on a stretcher and coded as emergency.

Table 4: Emergency Rates are Affected by the Policy Change on Weekends

	(1) Coded emerg.	(2) same (1) only weekend	(3) same (1) only weekdays	(4) Real emerg.	(5) same (4) only weekend	(6) same (4) only weekdays
Intercept	0.5183 (0.0128)***	0.8259 (0.0177)***	0.4882 (0.0135)***	0.1371 (0.0042)***	0.2124 (0.0115)***	0.1298 (0.0044)***
2012	-0.0364 (0.0173)*	-0.1069 (0.0266)***	-0.0307 (0.0182)	-0.0538 (0.0049)***	-0.0894 (0.0134)***	-0.0505 (0.0051)***
2013	-0.0372 (0.0182)*	-0.0748 (0.0203)***	-0.0343 (0.0191)	-0.0554 (0.0050)***	-0.0904 (0.0131)***	-0.0521 (0.0052)***
non-APDRG Hospital	-0.0938 (0.0171)***	-0.0350 (0.0243)	-0.0939 (0.0177)***	0.0581 (0.0070)***	0.1932 (0.0213)***	0.0481 (0.0071)***
ATET 2012	0.0292 (0.0232)	0.0524 (0.0333)	0.0273 (0.0241)	-0.0074 (0.0084)	-0.0433 (0.0250)	-0.0048 (0.0085)
ATET 2013	0.0464 (0.0241)	0.0483 (0.0285)	0.0455 (0.0250)	0.0011 (0.0085)	-0.0334 (0.0251)	0.0032 (0.0086)
Adj. R ²	0.0074	0.0113	0.0076	0.0228	0.0654	0.0203
Num. obs.	189674	26871	162803	189674	26871	162803
RMSE	0.7140	0.4804	0.7264	0.4230	0.4679	0.4109

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. indicating significance levels with standard errors

Source:

All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group. Furthermore grouping according to the description in chapter 3.

All DiD coefficients are calculated based on the pre-implementation year 2011 compared with the first year after the implementation 2012.

Note:

We use the weighting factor of n where n represents the number of cases per aggregated group.

All models use robust s.e. and p-values.

Models use the respective outcome in the model title (weighted) per case group.

Model (1) using year 2011 and 2012.

Model (2) using all available years which shows the same insignificant negative direction of the effect diluting predictability.

Model (3) using all available years which shows the same insignificant negative direction of the effect diluting predictability.

Model (4) using years 2011 and 2013 portraying an supposed term effect like in a placebo model.

ATET denotes an interaction term combined of the year and the treatment group as dummies representing the average treatment effect of the treated.

The models discussed so far do not consider any disturbance by other fixed effects (FE). The nature of our data would sustain the assumption that the case grouping by DRG influences the results. In Table 5, we display those effects in the baseline models applying DRG as FE, as has been done in Gauré(2013).

Table 5: Fixed Effects (DRG) DiD Models with Robust Estimates

	(1) Mortality	(2) # Diagnostic Codes	(3) Coded Emergency	(4) Real Emergency
2012	0.0024 (0.0013)	0.2126 (0.0263)***	-0.0519 (0.0028)***	-0.0719 (0.0021)***
2013	-0.0012 (0.0012)	0.2709 (0.0266)***	-0.0469 (0.0028)***	-0.0756 (0.0021)***
non-APDRG Hospital	0.0015 (0.0013)	0.1449 (0.0267)***	-0.0128 (0.0030)***	0.1092 (0.0028)***
ATET 2012	-0.0020 (0.0019)	0.0757 (0.0385)*	0.0319 (0.0042)***	-0.0129 (0.0036)***
ATET 2013	0.0007 (0.0018)	0.0424 (0.0384)	0.0329 (0.0042)***	-0.0009 (0.0036)
Num. obs.	189674	189674	189674	189674
Adj. R ² (full model)	0.2045	0.4181	0.3686	0.2157

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. indicating significance levels with standard errors

Source:

All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group. Furthermore grouping according to the description in chapter 3.

Note:

All models are estimated using the respective factor contained in the model title applying the discussion in (Gauré, 2013, p.106) to estimate the FE and use the outcome in respective title (1) to (4), and use robust s.e. and p-values. They do not contain any intercept because they are implicitly calculated in the factors as described by the author.

We use the weighting factor of n , where n represents the number of cases per aggregated group.

We deem it not necessary to further control for confounders as we have not seen any major improvement of the estimator's quality in the mortality rate section.

ATET denotes an interaction term combined of the year and the treatment group as dummies representing the average treatment effect of the treated.

Contrary to our above discussion displayed in Tables 2, 3, and 4 inferred effects in Table (5) validate intuition and the arguments in our above descriptive section 5.1 recognized. The significant effects in models (2) to (4) indicate a policy effect interpreted as a quality improvement. Summarizing the above, we conclude that mortality rates have not seen any effect but the other identified transparency-oriented quality measures have been touched by the policy. The number of diagnostic codes has seen an increase, as has the coded emergency cases, whereas the real emergency cases have reduced in number. These findings align with our intuition,

where we assume that quality in the system increases through more appropriate documentation. Furthermore, weekdays influence results further, whereas weekends appear to converge in quality of help care provision, at least for some medical areas (i.e., EoC). The policy has thus reinforced the general tendencies without being the sole reason.

Investigating the parallel trend assumption, which is graphically supported by quarterly trends that have occurred in both groups (refer to figures 8 and 9). Furthermore, we have applied the method used by Autor(2003) in Table 8. By integrating the pre-treatment as well as the post-policy quarters as dummies in the model, holding quarter four of 2011 as our reference (J.-S. Pischke, 2016; J.-S. Pischke, 2005, similarly to), we aim to show the parallel trend assumption and the effect's perseverance after the implementation year (Equation 2). We see that in conformity with the shown data and figures, there is a convergence of our counterfactual and treatment group, despite them having a structurally different rate level for the single parameters.

Adding covariates improves R^2 implicitly, thus reducing potential omitted variable bias. This becomes particularly apparent for the administrative (model 5) and clinical factors (model 7) in Table 2 for more detail see 7 in the appendix. The explanatory factor increases compared to the parsimonious model (1) but the DiD effect size is diluted when the covariate is introduced into the models. In order to increase the explanatory power of our model, we would have to integrate more institutional information not available within the data we have at hand. This would require us to pursue alternative approaches, such as those used by (Abadie, Diamond and Hainmueller, 2007). Due to hospital identification matters, we had to restrict our analysis to university hospitals, which appears to be a clear disadvantage. However, due to the specific clinical and wide healthcare service character of university hospitals in Switzerland, this should not represent a major issue in concluding general policy effects. University hospitals combine medical school cases with elective and emergency patients. Thus, the results should be comparable to the remaining hospitals, despite small area differences. This, however, could though be an artefact due to differing reporting behaviors. On the other hand, there are no restrictions in admission or other influencing factors in our data that could be observed, which would hint at a specific character of this type of hospital, apart them being a medical school. Furthermore, we assume that the reporting capabilities are the most progressed in those large institutions, and would present a higher reporting quality and compliance to official requirements than in other clinics. Below, we conclude with a summary of our findings in the context of the literature.

6 Discussion

Intuitively, the above results correspond to a general perception and expectancy towards the system change from a descriptive and quantitative point-of-view.

We also see that the model's basic assumptions are kept and are robust as far as our data allows. Regrouping all data to one reference catalog version (similar to the corrective approach Schreyögg et al., 2014), thus enabling single case analyses, and after that aggregation. One gains

consistency in comparison of effects through time. Further investigations are made difficult because of the lack of data connectivity, for example into mortality statistics allowing an international comparison. Regarding mortality, we detected no effect, such as can be observed in the LOS reduction by the policy change, which is muffled by the long-term development (compare Jucker, 2015; Busato and von Below, 2010). On the other hand, we see that analyzing the different outcome dimensions results within the quality continuum. First, from a clinical point-of-view, it appears that the system has not been affected by the policy change. The ultimate measure, mortality rates, seem not to have been affected by the policy change. At least the levels appear to remain stable and even converge to a certain baseline level. However, this effect should be observed in the long-term, as our data sample might be limited in that respect. Second, process or system quality dimensions have seen a significant change in that the increase of coding quality can be observed immediately after the implementation and even when comparing data at 1 year after inception. Documentation appears to play an important role within the system and receives the respective attention from the system's stakeholders while coding. Third, we observe the system's reaction to the two emergency admissions rates, reducing overall but increasing for the coded ones at the treatment group level and decreasing for the 'real' emergencies. Both are significantly influenced by the policy change. The interesting aspect represents the fact that, compared to the pre-existing DRG system environment, the rates changed substantially and conversely in the treatment group they more or less kept levels. This leads to the overall described policy effects. As no other spillover effects can be observed in the local systems, it seems that only the policy substantially influenced the coded emergencies. Despite its potentially harmful effects, such as increased reimbursements, this can be interpreted as an increase in transparency through improved documentation quality. The last and fourth consequence of the policy change is on weekend admissions, which have not been altered in general but, when combined with emergencies, there has been an amplifying effect. Intuitively, such a reaction could be expected, at least partly. However, the magnitude shows the new regime impacting on the precision of coding, which on weekends has also been increased in the non-APDRG hospitals. However, the veracity of "real" emergencies has also apparently improved, or patient referrals have been directed to other hospital types. On the other hand, one would expect a certain homogeneity over time in the effect size, as well as efficiency and quality of clinical care provided. We propose that mortality rates should enable us to precisely highlight such developments. However, this is not entirely the case, and differences persist in the ratio's level, which remains unexplained. We suspect that there is a certain level of endogeneity we cannot properly assess with the data. Albeit, we omit potential explanatory variables in our analysis that could jointly determine our outcomes, which is also why the covariate vectors are selectively defined.

Despite the limitations of our data set, this causal effect has immediate consequences for the system and the measurement of the policy's performance. We can sustain the hypothesis above that the overall quality of the system has been improved through the new policy. This fact would have to be further explored in continued work, especially involving a longer time series.

Nevertheless, from a policy perspective, our findings are the first to indicate effects on both quality of care provided and a more systemic level of quality. However, these findings are preliminary, and the coming stages of the policy will prove the validity of our claim. This might also be reason enough to avoid a magnitude estimate on the factors as in another attempt on the quantitative development of the policy consequences by P. Widmer, P. Hochuli, et al.(2017) who, if at all, found only small effect sizes, and instead focus on the effect as a result itself. Nor can we properly assess long-term effects that would be worthwhile in an assessment, and presumably exist. Additional external effects due to the structure of medical cases (e.g., unobserved severity), health literacy or other factors that enter the hospital's, are difficult to account for. Nevertheless, in our analysis, we have attempted to structure the models accordingly, and the two groups do not appear to account for fundamental differences in their observed structures.

Thus, we see that transparency has been increased due to the system change with more accurate diagnosis coding and more precise handling (i.e., coding of emergency admissions in acute inpatient care) and that mortality has not been altered by the policy change. Thus, we conclude the policy change has been beneficial for healthcare providers in Switzerland.

From a managerial point-of-view, decisions on optimization of clinical processes are largely driven by the payment system in place. It should also be the case that by the effort increase to code, more accurately should lead to a better outcome at the hospital result level. The only slightly increased case weights in Table 1 would indicate otherwise or only explain at a low level the single hospital's economic interest to apply consistent coding.

Using the same indicators in other country contexts can be done straightforwardly. Either using a reference catalog, as in our case, or by creating weighted averages for certain treatment groups, and in both cases deriving the ratio accordingly.

Eventually, our papers offer the groundwork for such health policy enhancing investigations, with several novel approaches and an innovation framework of data interpretation.

7 Summary Data

Table 6: Data Set Characteristics

Variable	Levels	n	\bar{x}	\tilde{x}	s	Min	Max
Age	APDRG	355227	47.514	47.514	0.000	47.514	47.514
	non-APDRG	202792	51.351	51.351	0.000	51.351	51.351
	all	558019	48.909	47.514	1.845	47.514	51.351
Female	APDRG	355227	0.508	0.508	0.000	0.508	0.508
	non-APDRG	202792	0.510	0.510	0.000	0.510	0.510
	all	558019	0.509	0.508	0.001	0.508	0.510
LOS	APDRG	355227	6.747	6.747	0.000	6.747	6.747
	non-APDRG	202792	6.650	6.650	0.000	6.650	6.650
	all	558019	6.711	6.747	0.047	6.650	6.747
LOSC	APDRG	355227	2.129	2.129	0.000	2.129	2.129
	non-APDRG	202792	1.977	1.977	0.000	1.977	1.977
	all	558019	2.074	2.129	0.073	1.977	2.129
Inpatient Mortality Rate	APDRG	355227	0.021	0.021	0.000	0.021	0.021
	non-APDRG	202792	0.021	0.021	0.000	0.021	0.021
	all	558019	0.021	0.021	0.000	0.021	0.021
Emergency Rate (coded)	APDRG	355227	0.494	0.494	0.000	0.494	0.494
	non-APDRG	202792	0.425	0.425	0.000	0.425	0.425
	all	558019	0.469	0.494	0.033	0.425	0.494
Emergency Rate (real)	APDRG	355227	0.101	0.101	0.000	0.101	0.101
	non-APDRG	202792	0.157	0.157	0.000	0.157	0.157
	all	558019	0.121	0.101	0.027	0.101	0.157
Number of Treatments	APDRG	355227	4.595	4.595	0.000	4.595	4.595
	non-APDRG	202792	5.192	5.192	0.000	5.192	5.192
	all	558019	4.812	4.595	0.287	4.595	5.192
Number of Diagnosis	APDRG	355227	3.904	3.904	0.000	3.904	3.904
	non-APDRG	202792	4.170	4.170	0.000	4.170	4.170
	all	558019	4.001	3.904	0.128	3.904	4.170

Source:

All hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment (DRG) and non-treatment group (APDRG).

Note:

The numbers above are aggregated per Level i.e. hospital type and weighted.

The table show mean, average, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values.

Emergencies are the number of cases classified as such upon hospital admission. Emergency (real) are the ones that are admitted by ambulance services to the hospital i.e. that do not walk into the service independently and are being admitted on a stretcher.

The inpatient mortality rate represent the cases that die within their stay at the hospital. We cannot distinguish cases that died outside of the inpatient stay i.e. 30 days mortality.

8 Model Results

Table 7: DiD Model Using Mortality and All Covariate Information

	(1) DiD Model (weighted)	(2) Same (1) only weekend	(3) Same (1) only weekdays	(4) Patient Confounders	(5) Administrative Confounders	(6) Same (5) incl. EOC	(7) Clinical all confounders	(8) Placebo (Q42011 & Q12013)
Intercept	0.0197 (0.0007)***	0.0409 (0.0030)***	0.0176 (0.0007)***	0.0020 (0.0008)**	-0.0019 (0.0009)*	-0.0015 (0.0008)	-0.0379 (0.0015)***	0.0201 (0.0015)***
Basic Model								
2012	0.0023 (0.0011)*	-0.0059 (0.0039)	0.0030 (0.0011)**	0.0023 (0.0009)**	0.0015 (0.0009)	0.0012 (0.0008)	0.0011 (0.0013)	0.0036 (0.0022)
2013	0.0007 (0.0011)	-0.0042 (0.0039)	0.0011 (0.0011)	0.0006 (0.0009)	-0.0003 (0.0009)	-0.0006 (0.0009)	-0.0021 (0.0013)	
non-APDRG Hospital	0.0002 (0.0011)	0.0014 (0.0045)	0.0004 (0.0011)	-0.0019 (0.0009)*	-0.0009 (0.0009)	-0.0014 (0.0009)	-0.0046 (0.0014)***	0.0002 (0.0023)
ATET 2012	-0.0006 (0.0016)	0.0062 (0.0061)	-0.0012 (0.0017)	-0.0007 (0.0013)	0.0000 (0.0013)	0.0001 (0.0013)	0.0016 (0.0020)	-0.0027 (0.0033)
ATET 2013	0.0011 (0.0016)	0.0019 (0.0061)	0.0010 (0.0017)	0.0006 (0.0013)	0.0013 (0.0013)	0.0013 (0.0013)	0.0045 (0.0019)*	
Patient Data								
Female				-0.0100 (0.0007)***	-0.0101 (0.0007)***	-0.0072 (0.0007)***	-0.0035 (0.0013)**	
Age2				0.0000 (0.0000)***	0.0000 (0.0000)***	0.0000 (0.0000)***	0.0000 (0.0000)***	
Administrative Data								
Pat. Class				0.0237 (0.0011)***	-0.0103 (0.0006)***	0.0212 (0.0011)***	-0.0081 (0.0011)***	
Weekend Admiss.				0.0072 (0.0011)***	0.0237 (0.0011)***	0.0426 (0.0025)***	0.0426 (0.0025)***	
HO				0.0089 (0.0008)***	0.0089 (0.0008)***	0.0068 (0.0011)***	0.0125 (0.0019)***	
LO				-0.0126 (0.0012)***	-0.0126 (0.0012)***	0.0102 (0.0008)***	0.0158 (0.0012)***	
Mov.				-0.0185 (0.0020)***	-0.0185 (0.0020)***	-0.0141 (0.0011)***	-0.0168 (0.0017)***	
NV						-0.0288 (0.0037)***	-0.0504 (0.0081)***	
EoC								
AMI						0.0275 (0.0021)***	0.0281 (0.0026)***	
CHF						0.0386 (0.0021)***	0.0276 (0.0022)***	
Choleystectomy						-0.0072 (0.0016)***	-0.0006 (0.0033)	
Hernia						-0.0170 (0.0011)***	-0.0047 (0.0031)	
Hip						-0.0205 (0.0017)***	-0.0124 (0.0026)***	
Knee						-0.0237 (0.0009)***	-0.0112 (0.0017)***	
Pulmonary						0.0140 (0.0014)***	0.0109 (0.0014)***	
Stroke						0.0436 (0.0020)***	0.0436 (0.0025)***	
Clinical Data								
Charlson Comorbidity							0.0141 (0.0004)***	
Adj. R ²	0.0000	0.0001	0.0001	0.0196	0.0247	0.0340	0.0538	0.0001
Num. obs.	189674	26871	162803	189674	189674	189674	101841	31727
RMSE	0.2107	0.2447	0.2043	0.2086	0.2081	0.2071	0.2342	0.2125

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, indicating significance levels with standard errors

Source: All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group. Furthermore grouping according to the description in chapter 3 using hospital mortality rates as outcome variable.

Note:

Models use the respective years for comparison i.e. implementation effect 2012 is based on data of 2011 and 2012 omitting 2013. That is why the number of observations differ. We use the weighting factor of n where n represents the number of cases per aggregated group.

All models use robust s.e. and p-values.

All DiD coefficients are calculated based on the pre-implementation year 2011 compared with the first quarter 2012. Including all covariates described. Model (1) represents the weighted baseline model comparing 2011 weighted mortality to the first quarter 2012. (2) shows a model based on weekend data only. Model (3) shows a model based on weekday data only. (4) adds patient specific covariates to the model (1) like gender and age. (5) describes the patients administrative data like insurance status, the referring body, weekend admission, status of the patient's length of stay status. Model (6) adds EoC as we suspect them to influence our results acknowledging the addition auto-collinearity to the model the dummy variable reference are "Other" cases nor in the selected list. Model (7) adds the Charlson Comorbidity Index as reference clinical indicator to the model. Model (8) applies DiD on last period 2011 and first period 2013 to simulate a placebo effect.

Variables:

Pat. Class = Mandatory insured patients as reference category and Semi-Private and Private Insured as remainder

Weekend Admiss. = Patient Admission on a weekend day either Saturday or Sunday

HO = High Outlier Case (reference Inlier) ; LO = Low Outlier Case (reference Inlier) ; Mov. = Binding transfer deduction; NV = Not validated as an Outlier Case

CHF = Congestive heart failure (reference EoC category = "Others");

Charlson Comorbidity = Grouped Charlson Comorbidity Index (Charlson et al., 1987);

ATET denotes an interaction term combined of the year and the treatment group as dummies representing the average treatment effect of the treated.

9 Parallel Trends and Fixed Effects Model

General model displaying parallel trend and continuous effect(J.-S. Pischke, 2016; J.-S. Pischke, 2005; Autor, 2003)

$$Mortality_{ist} = \lambda_s + \tau_t + \sum_{j=-m}^q \beta_j D_{st+j}(t = k + j) + X_{ist}\delta + \epsilon_{ist} \quad (2)$$

Note:

Where λ_s represents the time fixed effect and τ_t the state fixed effect i.e. the non-APDRG type hospital. In the interaction term $\beta_j D_{st+j}(t = k + j)$ k denotes the period in which the policy change takes place. m and q are the respective leads and lags of the treatment effect. The β coefficient is the j th lead or lag. The models apply a methodology used in (Autor, 2003). X_{ist} would be stat specific parametric time trends which we will not use and are merely noted for completeness reasons.

Table 8: Fixed effects models displaying parallel trends

	(1) Weighted DiD Mortality	(2) DiD - FE (DRG) Mortality	(3) DiD - FE (DRG) Diagnostic Codes	(4) DiD - FE (DRG) Coded Emergency	(5) DiD - FE (DRG) Real Emergency	(6) DiD - FE (DRG) Case Weight
Intercept	0.0190 (0.0012)***					
Quart. 4 2013	0.0032 (0.0020)	0.0037 (0.0013)**	0.2586 (0.0490)***	-0.0362 (0.0088)***	0.0752 (0.0055)***	-0.0372 (0.0100)***
non-APDRG Hospital	0.0007 (0.0017)	0.0008 (0.0011)	0.0974 (0.0483)*	0.0043 (0.0092)	0.0031 (0.0040)	-0.0215 (0.0102)*
Quart. 2 2011	0.0008 (0.0017)	0.0007 (0.0011)	-0.1585 (0.0467)***	0.0085 (0.0088)	0.0109 (0.0045)*	-0.0256 (0.0106)*
Quart. 3 2011	0.0010 (0.0017)	0.0013 (0.0011)	-0.2939 (0.0471)***	0.0119 (0.0091)	0.0099 (0.0043)*	-0.0142 (0.0116)
Quart. 4 2011	0.0046 (0.0017)**	0.0036 (0.0012)**	0.1028 (0.0509)*	-0.0403 (0.0073)***	-0.0517 (0.0041)***	-0.0131 (0.0103)
Quart. 1 2012	0.0019 (0.0017)	0.0020 (0.0012)	0.0865 (0.0523)	-0.0348 (0.0074)***	-0.0548 (0.0044)***	0.0028 (0.0112)
Quart. 2 2012	0.0022 (0.0017)	0.0025 (0.0012)*	-0.0367 (0.0519)	-0.0289 (0.0072)***	-0.0506 (0.0043)***	-0.0075 (0.0110)
Quart. 3 2012	0.0028 (0.0017)	0.0029 (0.0012)*	-0.0565 (0.0501)	-0.0338 (0.0072)***	-0.0401 (0.0040)***	-0.0082 (0.0100)
Quart. 4 2012	0.0012 (0.0017)	0.0004 (0.0012)	-0.0326 (0.0507)	-0.0324 (0.0069)***	-0.0497 (0.0042)***	-0.0179 (0.0104)
Quart. 1 2013	0.0009 (0.0017)	0.0005 (0.0011)	0.0292 (0.0516)	-0.0358 (0.0069)***	-0.0527 (0.0044)***	-0.0171 (0.0105)
Quart. 2 2013	0.0019 (0.0017)	0.0013 (0.0012)	0.0703 (0.0536)	-0.0295 (0.0070)***	-0.0476 (0.0045)***	-0.0111 (0.0108)
Quart. 3 2013	0.0012 (0.0017)	0.0010 (0.0011)	0.0211 (0.0507)	-0.0356 (0.0070)***	-0.0514 (0.0045)***	-0.0083 (0.0119)
ATET Q2 2011	-0.0046 (0.0029)	-0.0025 (0.0018)	-0.0855 (0.0718)	0.0109 (0.0128)	0.0087 (0.0087)	0.0252 (0.0138)
ATET Q3 2011	-0.0045 (0.0029)	-0.0028 (0.0018)	0.2815 (0.0741)***	-0.0038 (0.0127)	0.0070 (0.0090)	0.0302 (0.0152)*
ATET Q4 2011	-0.0030 (0.0029)	-0.0026 (0.0018)	0.4401 (0.0751)***	-0.0080 (0.0128)	-0.0094 (0.0083)	0.0174 (0.0148)
ATET Q1 2012	-0.0058 (0.0029)*	-0.0040 (0.0019)*	0.0595 (0.0744)	0.0365 (0.0114)**	-0.0075 (0.0069)	0.0173 (0.0145)
ATET Q2 2012	-0.0036 (0.0029)	-0.0028 (0.0018)	0.2072 (0.0770)**	0.0284 (0.0111)*	-0.0056 (0.0070)	0.0169 (0.0156)
ATET Q3 2012	-0.0043 (0.0029)	-0.0049 (0.0019)*	0.3843 (0.0761)***	0.0251 (0.0110)*	0.0008 (0.0072)	0.0228 (0.0149)
ATET Q4 2012	-0.0006 (0.0029)	-0.0010 (0.0019)	0.2553 (0.0726)***	0.0337 (0.0107)**	-0.0117 (0.0069)	0.0209 (0.0139)
ATET Q1 2013	-0.0001 (0.0029)	0.0002 (0.0019)	0.3619 (0.0719)***	0.0226 (0.0105)*	-0.0062 (0.0069)	0.0285 (0.0141)*
ATET Q2 2013	-0.0031 (0.0029)	-0.0032 (0.0018)	0.2654 (0.0725)***	0.0388 (0.0100)***	-0.0016 (0.0070)	0.0324 (0.0143)*
ATET Q3 2013	-0.0021 (0.0029)	-0.0019 (0.0018)	0.2273 (0.0746)**	0.0505 (0.0103)***	0.0026 (0.0072)	0.0107 (0.0136)
ATET Q4 2013	-0.0024 (0.0029)	-0.0023 (0.0018)	0.2205 (0.0716)**	0.0608 (0.0102)***	0.0061 (0.0072)	0.0141 (0.0151)
Adj. R ²	0.0000					
Num. obs.	189674	189674	189674	189674	189674	189674
Adj. R ² (full model)		0.2760	0.5467	0.6010	0.3265	0.8352

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. indicating significance levels with standard errors

Source:

All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group.

Note: The models apply a methodology used in (Autor, 2003).

We use the weighting factor of n where n represents the number of cases per aggregated group.

All models use robust s.e. and p -values.

Models use the respective outcome in the model title (weighted) per case group.

Model (1) using weighted DiD model containing all quarters.

Model (2) - (6) using weighted DiD model with respective outcome variable in the title of the model containing all quarters using fixed effects (FE) on DRG.

ATET denotes an interaction term combined of the year and quarter and the treatment group as dummies representing the average treatment effect of the treated: (ATET Q4 2013) - Treatment Group (non-APDRG hospitals) * Quarter 4 of 2013.

Figures highlighting prior parallel trends

Figure 8: Quarterly Development of Number of Cases in University Hospitals

Note:

The figure displays the neutralized five Swiss university hospitals quarterly cases' number development split in APDRG and non-APDRG.

It generally shows the relatively stable case development in Switzerland.

Figure 9: Showing Parallel Trends for Variables in the Data

Source:

All university hospitals based on Swiss Hospital Statistics (2011-2013) after cleaning and splitting in treatment and non-treatment group.

Note:

The graphs show parallel development of their values in the prior implementation quarters. The visual differences in (7) and (5) are most probably due to slight divergence in data compilation or unclean data collection.

10 R Packages and Environment Used

Analysis has been undertaken with the R version and packages below with the following versions:

- R version 3.4.2 (2017-09-28), x86_64-apple-darwin15.6.0
- Running under: macOS High Sierra 10.13.1
- LAPACK:
`/Library/Frameworks/R.framework/Versions/3.4/Resources/lib/libRlapack.dylib`
- Base packages: base, datasets, graphics, grDevices, grid, methods, stats, utils
- Other packages: bindrepp 0.2, cowplot 0.9.1, dplyr 0.7.4, forcats 0.2.0, Formula 1.2-2, ggfortify 0.4.1, ggplot2 2.2.1, ggthemes 3.4.0, gridExtra 2.3, gtable 0.2.0, Hmisc 4.0-3, icd 2.3.1, lattice 0.20-35, MASS 7.3-47, purrr 0.2.4, readr 1.1.1, reshape2 1.4.2, rms 5.1-1, scales 0.5.0, SparseM 1.77, stringr 1.2.0, survival 2.41-3, tibble 1.3.4, tidyr 0.7.2, tidyverse 1.2.1
- Loaded via a namespace (and not attached): acepack 1.4.1, assertthat 0.2.0, backports 1.1.1, base64enc 0.1-3, bindr 0.1, broom 0.4.2, cellranger 1.1.0, checkmate 1.8.5, cli 1.0.0, cluster 2.0.6, codetools 0.2-15, colorspace 1.3-2, compiler 3.4.2, crayon 1.3.4, data.table 1.10.4-3, DBI 0.7, digest 0.6.12, foreign 0.8-69, glue 1.2.0, haven 1.1.0, hms 0.4.0, htmlTable 1.9, htmltools 0.3.6, htmlwidgets 0.9, httr 1.3.1, jsonlite 1.5, knitr 1.17, latticeExtra 0.6-28, lazyeval 0.2.1, lubridate 1.7.1, magrittr 1.5, Matrix 1.2-11, MatrixModels 0.4-1, mnormt 1.5-5, modelr 0.1.1, multcomp 1.4-8, munsell 0.4.3, mvtnorm 1.0-6, nlme 3.1-131, nnet 7.3-12, parallel 3.4.2, pkgconfig 2.0.1, plyr 1.8.4, polyspline 1.1.12, psych 1.7.8, quantreg 5.34, R6 2.2.2, RColorBrewer 1.1-2, Rcpp 0.12.14, readxl 1.0.0, rlang 0.1.4, rpart 4.1-11, rstudioapi 0.7, rvest 0.3.2, sandwich 2.4-0, splines 3.4.2, stringi 1.1.6, TH.data 1.0-8, tools 3.4.2, xml2 1.1.1, yaml 2.1.14, zoo 1.8-0

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